

Serbian Association for Cancer Research

**5th CONGRESS OF SDIR:
TRANSLATIONAL POTENTIAL OF
CANCER RESEARCH IN SERBIA**

**ABSTRACT
BOOK**

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P32

Ursodeoxycholic acid influences antioxidative capacity in human breast adenocarcinoma cell line through Nrf2-dependent axis

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Background: The transcription factor, nuclear respiratory factor-2 (NRF2) is one of the main orchestrators of the cellular antioxidant response. The main objective of this *in vitro* study is to analyze the effects of ursodeoxycholic acid on the cytotoxic activity of doxorubicin, and the expression of NRF2 and antioxidant enzymes at the transcription level. **Material and methods:** MCF-7 cells were incubated for 24 h in a medium containing doxorubicin alone (0.25µM) or in combination with ursodeoxycholic acid (50µM). Cytotoxicity was determined using the MTT assay, whereas gene expression was determined using RT-qPCR method with beta-actin as a reference gene. Gene expression was analyzed using comparative Ct method, and statistical analysis was performed using one-way Anova and Tuckey's post-hoc test. **Results:** Incubation of MCF-7 cells with doxorubicin and ursodeoxycholic acid resulted in an increase in cytotoxicity compared to the group of cells incubated with doxorubicin only (p=0.005). Treatment of cells with doxorubicin significantly reduced the expression of *NRF2*, *SOD*, and *GR* compared to the control group (p<0.001; p<0.001; p=0.002, respectively). In the co-treated cells, the expression of *NRF2* was also significantly reduced (p=0.004), however, the expression of *SOD* and *GR* was highly statistically significantly reduced (p<0.001) compared to the group of cells incubated with doxorubicin only. **Conclusion:** Ursodeoxycholic acid and doxorubicin synergistically increased cytotoxicity in the MCF-7 cell line, by reducing the expression of *NRF2*, and its downstream targets, *SOD* and *GR* at the transcription level, aggravating redox homeostasis in malignant cells.

Key words: oxidative stress, bile acid, breast adenocarcinoma, doxorubicin, apoptosis

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